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“THE TALE OF GROWING ANCHORS”

The cap and gown, a borrowed honor,
A future map with vacant pages.
The lecture rooms, now a mere dying echo,
Where one has yet no solid footing.

The promised paths turn and sway.
"What next?" is a question, regardless.
The plans that are sheened lose their luster.
Waking from a structured dream.

A heavy chain, the burden of "then,"
A wordless scream against the rain.
All maps are vague, all signs are dwindling,
A lone journey, boldly taken.

Yet there is beauty in the mist.
In open roads and shifting skies.
Even if plans may halt and futures alter,
I'll discover inner peace and bliss within.